

FACTORS INFLUENCING COMMUNITY EXPOSURE TO AIR POLLUTION WITHIN WARRI REFINING AND PETROCHEMICAL COMPANY (WRPC) ENVIRONS, NIGERIA

Verere S. Balogun*, Peter O. A. Odjugo and Mary N. Ezemonye
Department of Geography and Regional Planning,
University of Benin, Benin City.

*Email of Corresponding Author: verere.sido@uniben.edu

Abstract

The study examined socio-economic factors which instigate and enhance exposure to pollution by residents of communities (Ubeji, Ifie-Kporo, Jeddo and Ekpan) around Warri Refining and Petrochemical Company of Nigeria (WRPC). Knowledge of such factors would provide basis for reducing exposure to pollution from point sources by enforcing planning regulations and extensive buffering around industries. The factors were determined using information retrieved from 379 copies of questionnaire, and analyzed descriptively using the Drivers, Pressures, State, Exposures, Effects and Actions (DPSEEA) framework. The results of the study revealed that refinery activities (32.5%) and a high proportion of migrant population (67.3%), the use of private owned electric power generating sets (74.%), vehicular traffic (2.4%) and bush burning (2.4%) were the major instigating factors which exposed residents to pollution in the study area. Family ties/ marriage (31.4%), employment and business opportunities (18.2%) and security and cheap housing (3.4%) were also reported to be the major reasons attracting new settlers to the area. The study recommends the enforcement of legislations reducing or banning emissions from industries and bush burning (37.5%), the use of alternative energy source (33.2%) and the use of 'controls in refinery processes (11.9%), in preventing and managing the factors which instigate and enhance exposure to pollution.

Keywords: Air Pollution; Exposure; Driving Force; Pressure; WRPC.

1. Introduction

Despite regulations prohibiting the location of residential units close to point sources of pollutants, various forms of settlement still spread around pollutant sources such as refineries (Khatatbeh, *et al*, 2020). Studies have shown that when such people are exposed to high amounts of toxic pollutants from a point source, their health and environment conditions are particularly affected (Ragothaman and Anderson, 2017; West *et al.*, 2020). The World

Health Organisation (WHO, 2017) defines air pollution as the “contamination of the indoor or outdoor environment by any chemical, physical or biological agent that modifies the natural characteristics of the atmosphere”. It has also been defined as the “introduction of chemicals, particulate matter, or biological materials into the atmosphere, which can cause harm or discomfort to humans or other living organisms, or cause damage to the natural environment” (Tawari and Abowei, 2012).

A petroleum refinery is an industry or processing plant which processes crude oil into various products such as diesel fuel, gasoline, heating oil, asphalt base, kerosene and liquefied petroleum gas. It comprises of large processors, in which crude oil is fractionally distilled and processed into valuable petroleum products. There are a number stacks of various vertical lengths extending upwards, linking various processing units which are used to disperse emissions at higher altitudes (Basorun and Olamiju, 2013). Though released at high altitudes, pollutant plumes settle to ground level at proximal distances from their source (Abdel-rahman, 2008). The crude oil refining process, which includes gas flaring in refineries releases substantial levels of gaseous and particulate pollutants into the atmosphere on daily basis, in addition to pollution from diesel trucks which lift petroleum products on regular basis, as well as thermal and noise pollution which usually accompany the operations of a typical refinery (Al-Hasnawi *et al.*, 2016; Ragothaman and Anderson, 2017).

As a result of emissions from oil refining activities including gas flaring, the health and socio-economic livelihood of the residents of the communities in their vicinity is severely affected. Poisonous chemical emissions reduce environmental quality by inducing acid rains, reducing soil fertility, pollution of underground and surface water and deterioration of the flora and fauna of ecologies. When humans are exposed to harmful substances in the atmosphere, they can suffer from diseases such as asthma, breathing difficulties, pains, chronic bronchitis and cancer. Benzene known to be emitted from gas flares in undocumented quantities is well recognized as a cause for leukaemia and other blood related diseases

(Akpan and Udo, 2016). Atmospheric pollution in refineries has also been linked to stunted growth in plants, resulting to lack of adequate food supply and acid rain among others (Basorun and Olamiju, 2013).

Previous studies have shown that emissions from refineries impact immensely on the health and physical environment of people residing in host communities. Studies by Nwachukwu *et al.* (2012); Obafemi *et al.*, (2012); Burr *et al.* (2018); West *et al.* (2020) and Khatatbeh *et al.* (2020) indicate that the health effects on residents living close to pollution sources may include diseases such as chronic bronchitis, pertussis, pulmonary, measles, tuberculosis, pneumonia, cancers, cerebrospinal meningitis (CSM) and upper respiratory tract infection. Winstrand (2009) and Vivian *et al.*, (2012) identified some of the socio-economic implications of living close to pollutant sources to include reduction in the value of housing property, increase in rent and crime rate. While previous studies have investigated the health, socio-economic and physical environmental impacts of refinery activities on host communities in other geographic locations with different ecologies and socio-economic backgrounds, the pre-disposing factors which enhance exposure to air pollution around WRPC have not been thoroughly explained. This study therefore focuses on the pre-disposing socio-economic factors which put people at risk of exposure to air pollutants from WRPC, located in Ubeji community of Warri-South Local Government Area, Delta State

This study therefore utilizes the Drivers, Pressures, State, Exposures, Effects and Actions (DPSEEA) model, which is a people oriented framework designed to analyse the

instigating factors and socio-economic implication of projects (WHO, 1999; Waheed *et al.*, 2009). This framework is a variant of the cause-effect relationship model designed to study impact of projects using a continuum beginning with “drivers” of environmental change (such as technology and population) to “pressures” (such as production, consumption and waste releases) to changes in environmental “state” (such as pollution levels) to “exposure” (such as external internal and target organ doses) to “effects” on health and environment. The framework also indicates possible “actions” to the outcomes at all levels, required to be undertaken by all sectors of government, private corporations and individuals towards preventing or controlling the effects of exposure to pollution from a point source (Steinle, 2012).

The effectiveness of implementing legislations towards reducing the risks of exposure to pollution from a point source would require knowledge on the predisposing factors which serve as the ‘driving force’ and ‘pressure’ behind the same problem. Following from this, the study aims at identifying the determinants or factors which serve as driving forces and added pressure to the problem of exposure to air pollution by community residents around WRPC of Nigeria. Results from the study would provide background for formulating policies, taking into cognizance the social and environmental determinants which serve as ‘driving force’ and ‘pressure’ to the problem of air pollution exposure. Knowledge of predisposing factors would provide insight for town/city administrators, on reducing the risks of exposure to pollution from point sources, taking into cognizance such background factors.

Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The host communities of WRPC which include Ubeji, Ifie-kporo, Jeddo, and Ekpan, are located in three L.G.As in Delta State. Ubeji and Ifie-Kporo communities are located in Warri-South LGA, Jeddo community is located in Okpe LGA, while Ekpan Community is located in Uvwie LGA (Figure 1). The combined population size of these four communities was estimated at 20,172 persons as at 1991 (NPC, 1991). This was projected to 48,118 persons as at 2018 (Table 1.), using 3.2% growth rate as stated by the National Population Commission, (NPC, 2010). The boundaries of WRPC are located on the coordinates 5⁰34’18” N, 5⁰34’19” N, 5⁰33’36” N, 5⁰33’35” N and 5⁰42’33” E, 5⁰43’19” E, 5⁰42’33” E and 5⁰43’25” E (Figure 1). The refinery covers a total land area of 1,104,014 hectares and is located in Ubeji community in Warri-South L.G.A. of Delta State (Basorun and Olamiju, 2013).

The economy of the area is very much associated with the refinery operations. Economic activities are usually in full swing most of the day and some parts of the night. The residents of host communities are mostly engaged in low to medium scale economic activities ranging from farming, fishing, basket weaving, fishing, illegal marketing of petroleum products, automobile repairs, Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) sales and distribution for household consumption, cosmetic and soap making, local gin brewing, furniture making, commercial transportation, trading etc. Many residents are also public servants and private firm employees. Non-residents with temporary stay are usually

engaged in activities relating to the lifting and transportation of petroleum products either from the refinery.

Figure 1. Uvwie, Okpe and Warri-South Local Government Areas (Inset Delta State)
 Source; Google Earth Imagery. Modified by Authors (2018)

2.

2 Data Analysis

In this study, primary and secondary spatial data were utilized. Primary data were derived from the administration of 381 copies of questionnaire, of which 99.5% (379 copies) were properly filled and utilized to obtain data on population, technology and socio-economic life of the inhabitants. These data which

constitute two ('driving force and 'pressure') of the five components of the DPSEEA framework were analysed using frequencies and percentages. Stratified sampling method was employed in allocating the copies of questionnaire to the four communities (Ekpan, Ifie Kporo, Jeddo and Ubeji) which made up the study area (Table 1).

Table 1. Population Figures of Selected Communities

SN	Communities	NPC Population Figures	1991 2018 Population Projections 3.22% Growth Rate)	Sample Size
1	Ekpan	16,852	40,200	318
2	Ifie Kporo	893	2,130	17
3	Jeddo	1,808	4,312	34
4	Ubeji	619	1,476	12
Total		20,172	48,118	381

Source: National Population Commission (NPC, 1991); National Population Commission of Nigeria (NPC, 2010)

Population projection was calculated using the formula $P_T = P_0 e^{k\Delta t}$.

Where:

P_T is population at time T

P_0 is population at time zero

K is growth rate and

Δt is elapsed time in years from time zero.

Sample size was determined using the table for sample size determination for a finite population by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), which specified a sample size of 381 for the projected population (48,118 persons) of the study area. Respondents were selected using the systematic sampling technique. In every housing unit selected, only one adult household

member was interviewed. In the event that adult members of a housing unit declined the task of responding to the questionnaire, the next housing unit became the subsequent housing unit for administering the questionnaire. Secondary data was derived from the National Population Commission and existing literature.

3. Results and Discussion

The determinants which serve as instigating factors and enhancers of the problem of exposure to air pollution in the study area was examined and presented using the first two stages of the DPSEEA framework, which comprise 'Drivers' and 'Pressure' stages. Stage one of the study involved identifying the circumstances or activities which instigate exposure of community residents around

WRPC to air pollution. Responses by respondents concerning the circumstances which prompted such exposure to an air polluting source were categorized into technological advancement, population growth and need for economic development. The results from the respondents in Table 2 identify

various technology and non-technology related activities which contribute to pollution in the selected communities. Refinery activities (32.5%) was mostly reported as the major instigating factor to the problem of air pollution exposure in the area, amongst other activities.

Table 2. Technology-based and Cultural Factors Contributing to Air Pollution around WRPC

S/N	Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Electric power generating sets/plants	29	7.4
2	Vehicular traffic	9	2.4
3	Refinery activities	123	32.5
4	Sewage and drainage systems	2	0.5
5	Bush burning	9	2.4
6	Farming and food processing technologies	1	0.3
7	Dump sites and open burning of municipal wastes	3	0.8
8	There is no contributing factor to air pollution	196	51.7
9	No response	8	2.1
Total		379	100

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2018

Other activities identified from the responses of respondents, which contribute to air pollution in the study include use of power generating sets (7.4%), vehicular traffic (2.4%), bush burning (2.4%), burning at dump sites (0.8%), sewage and drainages (0.5%) and food processing activities (0.3%) respectively. The activities indicated by respondents, which include refinery activities, operation of automobiles and power generating sets, are activities categorized as technological advancements, which entail the production and burning of fossil fuels. The operational activities of these technological equipment/projects in the study release pollutants, which may be associated with social and health problems within the host

communities. This result aligns with previous studies by Obafemi *et al.* (2012), which indicated that emissions from industries and vehicular traffic were the major source of pollution in Warri Township. Studies by Ragothaman and Anderson (2017); Manisalidis *et al.* (2020) also identified the petroleum industry, vehicular exhausts and coal burning as the major sources of air pollutants in inhabited areas.

More than half of the respondents (51.7%) insist that there is no contributing factor to the problem of exposure to air pollution, because they do not perceive their atmospheric environment as being polluted. This indicates low level of awareness of the problem of air pollution exposure and its causes. This

however negates findings by Obafemi *et al.* (2012) indicating affirmation by 72.4% of respondents that air pollution is a problem experienced by residents of Warri Township. The fact that people are reluctant to admit to the occurrence of air pollution in the study area may be associated with the fear that the realized

or anticipated socio-economic gain of living close to WRPC, might be lost upon initiation of pollution preventive measures. The assessment of 'Population Growth' as a 'Driving Force' behind Air Pollution Exposure is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Characteristics of Population of the Study Area

S/N	Status of Respondents	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Indigene	118	31.1
2	Migrant	255	67.3
3	No response	6	1.6
Total		379	100

The characteristics of the population in the study area indicate that 67.3% are migrants, who have been attracted to WRPC environs by reason of search for job opportunities and/or family ties. On the other hand, 31.1% of respondents are indigenous people born into the community. The fact that there are more migrant settlers compared to individuals born into the selected communities, indicates a higher rate of population increase, compared to areas with less migrant population. The

increasing population in the selected communities is also supported by the annual growth rate of 3.2% stated by the National Population Commission (NPC, 2010), which is one of the highest in Nigeria. High rate of population growth implies that increasing number of people are at risk of exposure to the problem of air pollution. Population growth is thus regarded as one of the major driving forces behind the problem of exposure to air pollution. The perceived role of WRPC in enhancing population increase is examined in Table 4.

Table 4. The Perceived Role of WRPC in Population Increase

S/N	Perception of Residents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	New settlers are attracted by existing population in the area	69	18.2
2	New settlers are attracted by the presence of WRPC	99	26.1
3	New settlers are attracted both by existing population and presence of WRPC	178	47.0
4	Presence of Security and cheap housing	13	3.4
5	Previous settlers are migrating away from WRPC	3	0.8
6	No response	17	4.5
Total		379	100

The results reveal that respondents are of the opinion that new settlers are attracted by ties to existing population in the area (18.2%), the presence of WRPC (26.1%), a combination of the reasons of ‘ties to existing population’ and the ‘presence of WRPC’ (47.0%) and the quest for cheap accommodation (3.4%). Increasing number of people resident in the communities around WRPC invariably increases the number of people who are exposed to air pollution from the refinery. Increasing population, resulting to population congestion, increases pressure and demand for energy resources and infrastructure. More demand for energy resources imply more production and burning of fossil fuels resulting in increased air pollution. These findings have been similarly

reported by Han *et al.* (2019), who observed that increased population owing to migration constituted a major proportion of the population exposed to pollution in a rapidly urbanizing area. The study by Winstrand (2009) revealing that property values were lower in the vicinities close to a refinery, confirms the responses of 3.4% of respondents, who revealed that the main reason for the choice of settling around WRPC, was to secure cheap housing facility. An assessment of socio-economic development as a driving force behind the problem of exposure to pollution yielded the results as presented in Table 5, showing combinations of various socio-economic reasons, governing choice of settling in the communities around WRPC.

Table 5. Socio-Economic Factors influencing Respondents’ Choice of Settling around WRPC

S/N	Reasons for Choice of Settlement	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Business/ Employment	69	18.2
2	Schooling	14	3.7%
3	Family ties and marriage	119	31.4
4	Business opportunities only	39	10.3
5	Family ties/Schooling	33	8.7
6	Family ties/Employment	34	9
7	Family ties and business opportunity	30	7.9
8	Presence of Security and cheap housing	13	3.4
9	Other personal reasons	15	4
10	No response	13	3.4
Total		379	100

The responses from respondents indicate that family ties/marriage (31.4%), quest for business opportunities and employment (18.2%) and business opportunities (10.3%) were the main factors governing the choice of settling in their respective communities. The

other factors identified as reasons for settling near WRPC are family ties and schooling (8.7%), family ties and employment (9.0%), family ties and business opportunities (7.9%), schooling (3.7%), security and cheap housing (3.4%) and other personal reasons (4%)

respectively. In the quest for socio-economic advantage, people are inadvertently exposed to air pollution from a point source. From the result, it can be seen that business opportunities, employment and family ties mostly inform the residents' choice of settling close to WRPC, as these are the major socio-economic factors which enhance the problem of exposure to air pollution. This results

corroborate with the study by Vivian *et al.* (2012), which revealed positive gains by residents living close to the refinery to include increase in commercial activities, infrastructural provisioning and social service rendition by the refinery management. The preventive actions against the problem of exposure to air pollution around WRPC at the 'driving force' stage is shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Preventive Actions Required at the 'Driving Force Stage'

S/N	Preventive Actions	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Use of improved and cleaner energy/technology	33	8.7
2	Enforcement of legislation reducing/banning emissions from industries and bush fires	142	37.5
3	Settlement relocation	4	1.1
4	No preventive action is required	196	51.7
5	No response	4	1.1
Total		379	100

The major preventive action supported by 37.5% of respondents was enforcement of legislation reducing/banning emissions from industries and bush fires. Other preventive actions include use of improved and cleaner energy/technology (8.7%), and settlement relocation (1.1%). These preventive actions have been similarly recommended by Ragothaman and Anderson (2017), who are of the opinion that policies and legislations on emission reduction should be backed by statistical modeling of the distributional consequence of emission reduction for different scenarios. Amann (2020) suggests that policies to curb emission should range from energy/climate policies, agricultural policies and emission control policies. Sofia *et al.* (2020) also opines that guidelines for

preventing and mitigating exposure to air pollution should be streamlined according to the various energy production/utilization sectors, which include transportation, industry, household, energy generation, agriculture, and shipping sectors. 51.7% of respondents were of the opinion that preventive action against air pollution in their communities is not required, because they do perceive their atmospheric environment to be polluted. This indicates low level of awareness of the problem of exposure to air pollution among residents of selected communities.

Stage two of the study involved identifying the 'added pressure' or enhancers of the problem of exposure to air pollution. In line with the DPSEEA model, these are the production, transportation and consumption of petroleum

products, resulting in waste release. Observations during the course of fieldwork revealed that production periods at WRPC were marked by the sighting of fires at the top of gas flare stacks in the sky horizon. Lifting of refined products by diesel trucks for consumption were periodic, as they were themselves sources of secondary pollutants and the major cause of traffic gridlocks. Automobiles which consume the refined

products from WRPC, also contribute secondarily to pollution in the environment. The actions required for managing the added pressure of continual production, consumption and waste generated from petroleum products are provided by respondents in Table 7. The most supported action required is the use of alternative energy source (33.2%), specifically hydroelectric power, as a substitute for fossil fuel use.

Table 7. Actions Required to Manage Added Pressure of Production and Consumption of Air Polluting Fuels

S/N	Management Actions	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Use of alternative energy source (hydro-electric power)	126	33.2
2	Use of control measures during refinery operations	45	11.9
3	Relocation of the refinery	8	2.1
4	No management action is required	196	51.7
5	No response	4	1.1
Total		379	100

The use of alternative energy source in managing the problems associated with the production, transportation and consumption is supported by Wuebbles and Sanyal (2015), whose study projected to year 2050, a clean-energy-use scenario as against fossil-fuel-use scenario. Their findings indicate that a shift from fossil powered energy sources to

renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power, would greatly improve air quality. Other actions required to manage production and consumption of air polluting fuels include use of control measures during refinery operations (11.9%) and relocation of the refinery (2.1%).

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

The results of the study indicate that emissions from industries, privately owned electric generating sets and vehicular traffic constitute major sources of pollution people are exposed to. An increasing migrant population attracted by the prospects of gainful business ventures,

family closeness or ties, educational facilities, security and cheap housing, exacerbate community exposure to air pollution in the vicinity around WRPC. Preventive and management policies and strategies adopted should be that which benefits all stakeholders. The results of the study suggest the need for enforcement of legislation reducing/banning

emissions from industries and bush fires, and the adoption of renewable alternative energy source. Industrial emission regulatory policies have been in existence, however emissions still remain unchecked. The reluctance in implementing policies reducing emissions may be tied to the high dependence of the Nigerian economy on revenue accrued from the petroleum industry. The Nigerian economy should be remodeled to reduce its dependence on fossil fuel production and uses. The process of change to reduce emissions should first be backed up with implementable policies, which

would provide guidelines for the gradual phasing out fossil fuel use within set timelines. At the same time, the economic development plans should be worked out to provide for alternative sources of revenue. In the short term, increasing number of migrants settling around refineries should be discouraged by establishing and strictly maintaining buffers around refineries. Individuals are also expected to adopt environmentally friendly behaviours such as avoiding bush burning and increased use of eco-friendly energy sources.

References

- Abdel-rahman, A. A. (2008). On the Atmospheric Dispersion and Gaussian Plume Model. In N. E. Mastorakis, M., Poulos, V., Mladenov, Z., Bojkovic, D., Simian, S., Kartalopoulos, A., Varonides, C., Udriste (Eds.), *Proceedings at the 2nd International Conference on Waste Management, Water Pollution, Air Pollution, Indoor Climate* (pp 31-39). Corfu, Greece: WSEAS press. Retrieved from <https://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/bitstream/1822/18821/1/wwai30a.pdf>
- Akpan, A. O. and Udo, H. I. (2016). Challenges of Air Pollution on Human Health in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Health Promotion*, 9.
- Al-Hasnawi, S. S., Hussain, H. M., Al-Ansari, N. and Knutsson, S. (2016). The Effect of the Industrial Activities on Air Pollution at Baiji and its Surrounding Areas, Iraq. *Engineering*, 8, 34-44. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/eng.2016.81004>
- Amann M., Kieseewetter, G., Schöpp, W., Klimont, Z., Winiwarer, W., Cofala, J., Rafaj, P. Pavarini, C. (2020). Reducing Global Air Pollution: The Scope for Further Policy interventions. *Philosophical Transactions Royal Society, A* (378), 20190331. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2019.0331>
- Basorun, J. O. and Olamiju, I. O. (2013). Environmental Pollution and Refinery Operations in an Oil Producing Region of Nigeria: A Focus on Warri Petrochemical Company. *Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology*, 2 (6), 18-23.
- Burr, W. S., Dales, R., Liu, L., Stieb, D., Smith-Doiron, M., Jovic, B., Kauri, L. M. and Shin, H. H. (2018). The Oakville Oil Refinery Closure and Its Influence on Local Hospitalizations: A Natural Experiment on Sulfur Dioxide. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15 (9),

2029.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15092029>
- Han, L., Zhou, W., Pickett, S. T. A., Li, W., and Qian, Y. (2019). Risks and Causes of Population Exposure to Cumulative Fine Particulate (PM2.5) Pollution in China. *Earth's Future*, 7, 615–622.
<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019EF001182>
- Khatatbeh, M., Alzoubi, K., Khabour, O., and Al-Delaimy, W. (2020). Adverse Health Impacts of Living near an Oil Refinery in Jordan. *Environmental Health Insights*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1178630220985794>
- Manisalidis, I., Stavropoulou, E., Stavropoulos, A. and Bezirtzoglou, E. (2020) Environmental and Health Impacts of Air Pollution: A Review *Front. Public Health* 8(14). <http://dx.doi:10.3389/fpubh.2020.00014>
- National Population Commission, NPC (1991). *Final Results of 1991 Population Census of Nigeria*. National Population Commission, Nigeria.
- National Population Commission, NPC (2010). *2006 Population and Housing Census, Priority Table Volume III: Population Distribution by Sex, State, LGA and Senatorial District*. National Population Commission, Nigeria.
- Nwachukwu, A. N., Chukwuocha, E. O. and Igbudu O. (2012) A survey on the effects of air pollution on diseases of the people of Rivers State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* Vol. 6(10), 371-379.
<http://www.academicjournals.org/AJEST>
- Obafemi, A. A., Eludoyin, O. S. and Akinbosola, B. M. (2012). Public Perception of Environmental Pollution in Warri, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 16 (3), pp. 233 – 240.
- Ragothaman, A. and Anderson, W. A. (2017). Air Quality Impacts of Petroleum Refining and Petrochemical Industries. *Environments*, 4 (66), 1-16.
<http://dx.doi:10.3390/environments4030066>
- Sofia, D., Gioiella, F., Lotrecchiano, N., and Giuliano, A. (2020). Mitigation Strategies for Reducing Air Pollution. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-08647-x>
- Steinle, S., Reis, S. and Sabel, C. E. (2012). Developing a Conceptual Model for the Assessment of Personal Exposure to Air Pollution. *2012 International Congress on Environmental Modeling and Software: Managing Resources of a Limited Planet*. International Environmental Modeling and Software Society (iEMSSs), Sixth Biennial Meeting, Leipzig, Germany.
<http://www.iemss.org/society/index.php/iemss-2012-proceedings>
- Tawari, C. C. and Abowei, J. F. N. (2012). Air Pollution in the Niger Delta Area of Nigeria. *International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 1(2), 94-117.
- Vivian, E. L., Blamah, V. N., Ezemokwe, I. (2012). Socio-economic Impact of the Kaduna Refining and Petrochemical Company (KPRC) on the Rido Area of

- Kaduna Metropolis. *Journal of Environmental Management and Safety*, 3 (5), 124-139.
- Waheed, B., Khan, F. and Veitch, B. F. (2009). Linkage-Based Frameworks for Sustainability Assessment: Making a Case for Driving Force-Pressure-State-Exposure-Effect-Action (DPSEEA) Frameworks. *Sustainability*, 1, 441-463; <https://doi:10.3390/su1030441>
- West, S. E., Büker, P., Ashmore, M., Njoroge, G., Welden, N., Muhoza, C., Osano, P., and Apondo, W. (2020). Particulate Matter Pollution in an Informal Settlement in Nairobi: Using Citizen Science to make the Invisible Visible. *Applied Geography*, 114 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2019.102133>.
- Winstrand, J. (2009). *The Effects of a Refinery on Property Values – The Case of Sweden*. Working Paper 2009:10, Department of Economics, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden.
- World Health Organisation (2017). *Air Pollution*. (Accessed online 14th May, 2019) http://www.who.int/topics/air_pollution/en/
- World Health Organization (1999). *Environmental Health Indicators: Framework and Methodologies*. Occupational and Environmental Health Series. WHO/SDE/OEH/99.10. Geneva: WHO
- Wuebbles, D. J. and Sanyal, S. (2015). Air Quality in a Cleaner Energy World. *Current Pollution Reports*, 1(2), 117–129. <http://dx.doi:10.1007/s40726-015-0009-x>